

Design, emotion and longer-lasting products - Deliver specific insights to designers how to create emotionally durable products

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Abstract In a world smothered in people and products, it must be questioned what all this 'meaningful stuff' is really for, and why does it transform into 'meaningless rubbish' so quickly? We produce 40 tonnes of waste to manufacture one tonne of electronic products. Of that tonne, 98% are discarded within just six months of purchase. Strategies like *emotionally durable design* help us explore the idea of creating a deeper, more sustainable bond between people and their material things; reducing the consumption and waste of resources by increasing the durability of relationships between users and products. This paper argues that emotionally durable design not only helps designers and manufacturers carve deeper pathways to resource efficiency, but also opens up new innovation possibilities for generating greater levels of brand loyalty and perceived value within customers. Using the metaphor of the ocean, this paper reframes products in terms of *depths* and *shallows* of our material experience; taking us from the handful of objects occupying the seldom seen, *hadal zone* of our deeper material world, to the abundance of material goods occupying the surface, or *epipelagic zone*.

Keywords *Emotional durability, Depth, User experience, Sustainability*

Introduction

Never before have we wanted, consumed and wasted so much. In a world smothered in people and products, it must be questioned what – beyond a conventional understanding of functionality – is all this 'meaningful stuff' really for, and why does it transform into 'meaningless rubbish' so quickly? According to the director of London's Design Museum, Deyan Sudjic, we live in a world drowning in objects (Sudjic, 2008); households with a TV set in each room; kitchen cupboards stuffed with waffle makers, blenders and cappuccino whisks, and drawers swollen with a plethora of pocket sized devices powered by batteries, which themselves are products that take several thousand times more energy to make, than they will ever produce.

The volume of waste produced by today's cyclical pattern of short-term desire and disappointment is a major problem, not just in terms of space and where to put it, but, perhaps more notably, for its toxic corruption of the biosphere. Rapidly rising consumption in newly industrialised countries such as China, India and Brazil puts further stress upon reserves of natural resources (Cooper, 2002). This is why the behavioural strategies like *emotionally durable design* (Chapman, 2005; 2015) are so vital in helping us explore the idea of creating a deeper, more sustainable bond between people and their material things. The ultimate aim is to reduce the consumption

and waste of resources by increasing the durability of relationships between consumers and products. After all, the crisis of unsustainability is a crisis of behaviour and perception, not one of energy and materials.

Considering emotional durability at the design stage helps us tackle the challenge of weaning people off their desire for the new, and helps shape new sustainable business models in which longer lasting products have the potential to present robust economic models for creating products, services and brand-loyal customers – driving future sales, upgrade, service and repair (United Nations, 2013). Take, for example, a toaster that lasts about 12 months. If you can extend that use-career to 18 months through emotionally durable design, you have bought about a 50% reduction in waste consumption in all the materials and energy and systems associated with the production and distribution of that product – this is a significant impact (Chapman, 2015).

A spaceship in your bathroom

The vast majority of resources taken out of the ground today become waste within only three months: waste comprising complex cocktails of plastics, metals and other synthetic compounds no longer recognisable to the microbial decomposers that degrade substances back to their basic nutritional building blocks. It may shock you to know that in terms of consumer

electronics – arguably one of the most impactful areas of design activity today – we produce 40 tonnes of waste to manufacture one tonne of products. Of that tonne of products, 98% are discarded within just six months of purchase. In terms of energy and material alone, this sequence of events is less than 1% efficient. Or, to put it another way, our prevailing system of production and consumption is over 99% inefficient. This, of course, is completely unacceptable and begins to explain why – in an ecological sense – we are in the perilous situation we are in. One might assume that, given the huge quantities of precious resources that find their way into our gadgets, we would take a little more care of them, fix them when they break and, indeed, keep them for longer periods of time. However, as we all know, this simply is not the case.

The majority of today's post-consumer waste (the stuff you and I chuck out) is currently disposed of via community recycling centres (ideal) and landfill sites (less ideal), which leak heavy metals and other toxic contaminants over time, such as arsenic, cadmium, copper, lead, manganese and zinc. These toxic elements find their way into soil and groundwater, threatening biodiversity. Landfills are also known to produce large volumes of methane (CH₄), a greenhouse gas and main contributor to climate change. In fact, CH₄ is 25 times more potent per kilo than CO₂. A smaller percentage of waste is burned using vast incinerators that produce ash, laden with toxic elements such as cadmium, lead, mercury, chromium, tin and zinc, while also releasing acidic gases such as sulphur dioxide and nitrous oxides into the atmosphere. Even the much acclaimed recycling of e-waste consumes large quantities of energy, while the chemicals involved during treatment and sorting often find their way back into the ecosystem, causing further damage. Furthermore, the system is not always as efficient and clean as we might assume. It's costly to separate materials that have been soldered onto circuit boards, and this complex form of e-waste – though responsibly sent for recycling by the user, on their way to the mall – ends up getting shipped to a developing country with little or no environmental law, where it is incinerated, and so the crisis worsens.

Precious elements like gold are surprisingly commonplace in electronic products, largely due to their excellent conductive capabilities. In terms of e-waste, there is more gold in a tonne of phones than there is in a tonne of rocks from a gold mine! This mind-boggling idea begins to shift our focus from waste management, to resource management, as the things we discard are materially resource, if only we designed them in a way for this material to be recovered at end-of-life. However, at present, the rock-bound gold is considered more economically viable to extract than its phone-bound counterpart. This kind of waste is a design flaw, if ever there was one. With rising resource costs, and mounting levels of legislation-driven producer responsibility, situations such as these must change.

I'm not just talking about high-tech products like smartphones and tablets here; even fairly low-tech and banal products like electric toothbrushes,

hairdryers and toasters are highly complex when understood from the perspective of their materials and ingredients. Indeed, they're more like likes spaceships! A cheap and disposable child's remote-control tank, for example, contains a thumbnail-sized microchip, within which you will find over two thirds of the elements of the periodic table. And let's not forget, these precious elements don't come out of the ground in clear glass test tubes, ready for use (think of the chemistry set you had when you were a kid). On the contrary, these rare compounds are mined and clawed from the earth, encased in thousands of tonnes of rock and mud. A complex, highly polluting and energy intensive process of extraction and purification follows, within which lurks the majority of our material world's ecological and social destruction. The plethora of electronic products that surround us are infused with a rich cocktail of complex minerals, precious metals and noxious compounds, which to most of us, are completely unseen, lurking just beneath the surface of our material experience.

Products are like icebergs

Products are like icebergs. They are vast, majestic and mysterious things. They are formed in ways that reflect their provenance, their origins. They don't last forever, but some last longer than others. Yet, as we all know, icebergs are potentially deadly too. There is the part you see, above the surface. Then, there is the part you don't see, below the surface, with the submerged part representing 90% of the total ice mass, or thereabouts. The social and ecological impacts of products are kind of similar. The product being the part of the iceberg you see, and the product's associated impact representing the part you don't see; this is by far the greater part, and also the part that is potentially deadly. As any sailor will tell you, the part of an iceberg you need to worry about is not the part you can see, but the greater, submerged parts.

Morton uses the term, *hyperobjects*, to refer to such things that are vastly distributed in time and space, relative to humans (Morton, 2014), and are both seen, and unseen. He tells us that: 'a hyperobject could be a black hole. A hyperobject could be the Lago Agrio oil field in Ecuador, or the Florida Everglades. A hyperobject could be the biosphere, or the Solar System. A hyperobject could be the very long-lasting product of human manufacture, such as Styrofoam or plastic bags, or the sum of all the whirring machinery of capitalism' (p2). These forms of object systems are all around it, yet as designers and users we tend to forget this. We don't look at the screens of our smartphones, for example, and simultaneously imagine complex networks of satellites orbiting our planet, relaying the signals we both emit and receive. Instead, we tend only to see the part of the product that we are engaging with, as opposed to the much broader infrastructure it sits within. Similarly, we don't tap the blue Facebook icon, and imagine an energy-hungry server in California pushing data on our behalf.

This is one of the thornier challenges for product design: to widen the user's field of vision, to encompass the whole object – the *hyperobject* –

including its relational system. Indeed, for product designers grappling with complex issues of *sustainable design* and *design for the circular economy* it is imperative that your field of vision grows as wide as it possibly can if we are to begin tackling this experiential disconnect. The way we relate to and experience our environment defies logic. We clear carbon absorptive forests, to grow methane-producing meat, and smother vast areas of bio diverse wilderness with ecologically inert urban sprawl, riddled with mazes of oil-dependent highways. This *epistemological error* (Bateson, 1972) tells us how the earth is finite, balanced, synergistic and reactive, and yet we design the world as though it were separable, mechanical and lasting. Indeed, human destruction of the natural world is a crisis of behaviour, and not one simply of energy and material alone, as is often assumed (Chapman, 2015); the decisions we make as an industry, the values we share as a society and the dreams we pursue as individuals collectively drive all that we accomplish, while shaping the ecological impact of our development as a species. This ecological crisis concerns how we think, and the institutions that purport to shape and refine the capacity to think (Orr, 2004, p2).

Never satisfied

The notion of a 'throwaway society' is nothing new. In fact, it was as early as 1932 when American economist Bernard London first introduced the term, 'planned obsolescence' (made popular by Vance Packard in his monograph *The Waste Makers* (1963)) as a means to stimulate spending among the very few that had money at that time. This proposed shift toward an increasingly disposable material world was initially proposed as a solution to dark economic crisis experienced during the Great Depression in the US (c.1929). However, the ecological impacts of this drive toward planned product failure could not have been anticipated or understood in the 1930s. Today, however, we are all too aware of the catastrophe-making character of these practices. As Slade forcefully argues in his book, *Made to Break: Technology and Obsolescence in America*, the concept of disposability was in fact a necessary condition for America's rejection of tradition and our acceptance of change and impermanence (Slade, 2007). By choosing to support ever-shorter product lives, he argues that we may well be shortening the future of our way of life as well, with perilous implications for the very near future. Just over a century ago, 'disposability' referred to small, low cost products such as disposable razors or paper napkins, whereas today it is culturally permissible to throw anything away anything from TV sets and vacuum cleaners to automobiles and an entire fitted bathroom (Chapman, 2013a). Like flotsam and jetsam, the waste generated through this inefficient system coat the surface of our material worlds, obscuring an otherwise rich set of encounters with the inanimate.

So why are we so perpetually dissatisfied with our things, and why is satisfaction such a utopian idea? The motivational drivers underpinning the act of consumption represent a way of being, of interacting with the world. We transfer resources into products

that provide us with existential mirrors, allowing us to view and experience our dreams and desires in real time. These reflections help us to construct an identity that we feel is individual, while also being indicative of our individual aspirations and dreams. In this respect, objects are meaningful in that they illustrate – both to society and the self – our personal life journeys. The process of consumption also appears to possess a quality of avoidance: by continually busying ourselves within a world of goods and services, we cunningly side step sensations of emptiness through sheer distraction – consumption gives us a sense of purpose, and belonging. However, these mirrors cast reflection that is both short lived, and distorted. The products we deploy to both the mirror and project this identity are relatively fixed in time, however.

Much perceived obsolescence is stimulated by this cycle, in which perfectly effective products seem somehow out-dated, and undesirable by the user, simply because they cast an out-dated reflection of who they were, rather than who they now are, or yearn to be. This continual and iterative process is often referred to as *hedonic adaptation* – the observed tendency of humans to quickly return to a relatively stable level of happiness despite major positive or negative events or life changes (Rosenbloom, 2010). Interestingly, *experiential purchases* (like a massage, a study programme or travel) take longer for us to adapt to and tend to hold value from the longer than *material purchases* (like a camera, a car or a jacket). This is because experiential purchases rely more on memory to be processed and understood, whereas material purchases are more tangible and are experienced in real time, and therefore considered less complex and easier to overcome. Of course, products and experiences are not entirely different things that this crude polarisation is helpful in seeing a distinction, which doesn't believe to some clues around the endurance of meaning and value in the things we consume.

Similarly, the *Diderot effect* (McCracken, 1988) is a social phenomenon that describes the unstable nature of our relationships with products. This theory describes how consumers are drawn to products that are experienced as reflecting their sense of identity. As a result, it is assumed that the products a given person buys will be somehow complementary to one another, as each object has been selected on a similar set of identity-matching criteria. However, as McCracken points out, the introduction of new possessions can disrupt the previously stable collection of complementary products. In other words, the Diderot effect helps explain the process whereby a new purchase creates dissatisfaction with existing possessions, triggering a spiralling pattern of consumption with hugely destructive environmental, psychological and social implications.

Socially approved patterns of behaviour shape the way we interact with the material world. There are a surprising number of such behaviours, or *norms*, which govern the way we value and use goods. Many of these are so inherent that we are unaware of their existence. Norms are cultural products (including

values, customs, and traditions) (Sherif, 1936), which represent individuals' basic knowledge of what others do and think that they should do (Cialdini, 2003). Sociologists describe norms as informal understandings that govern individuals' behaviour in society. It's very normal, for example, that this paper is written in English, and I will bet that this had not occurred to you until just now, when I mentioned it. Norms work in this way; they go unseen until someone draws attention to it, making it noticeable. Electricity works in this way, it's so normal that we only tend to notice it when it fails, flickers or cuts out entirely.

Norms also influence our perception of product lifespans, and how long our possessions ought to last; a toaster should last four years, a kettle five, a smartphone two and so on. None of us ever consciously decided this, but rather, we were socially conditioned to subscribe to these norms. They are massively influential in our decision-making processes relating to when a particular product should be replaced, or, if it breaks whether we fix it, or dump it. Yet, despite their prominence, norms can often be quite ridiculous. For example, replacing a smartphone because of a cracked screen makes no sense, yet many people do this; it's about as ridiculous as replacing an entire car because of a flat tyre. Both are equally repairable, yet one quite common practice, the other unthinkable.

The depths and shallows of material experience

As we dive downwards to the *hadal zone* (the deepest and least explored part of the ocean, where little life exists) we near the depths of our material worlds, in which the objects become increasingly personal, and idiosyncratic. In contrast to the abundant and heavily populated *epipelagic zone*, there are fewer products down here, things move slower and things seem all the more stable. Down here, on-trend fonts make way for handwritten notes; digital screens make way for torn notepaper and logotypes are elbowed aside by images of forgotten friends, lost family and jilted lovers. In the turbulent storms of material experience, these enduring objects serve to anchor us within a more constant identity, and we cling dearly to them.

Of course, we are each connected to several distinct systems of objects, occupying different depths of material experience. These objects may well sit side-by-side on our shelves, but are divided by fathoms, in an experiential sense. To an observer, the things we own and cherish may appear superfluous, banal, and even venal (Schultz et al., 1989) yet we cling to them because they possess significant levels of personal meaning that defines us individually, as separate from society. On describing the depth and power of inanimate objects, Bruce Hood, author of *Super Sense* (2009), undertook an experiment in which he first hands out a black 1930s fountain pen, which he falsely claimed, belonged to Albert Einstein. Everyone in the audience is desperate to hold it, and shows great reverence and awe toward the object, as though part of Einstein's soul somehow resided within it (Hood, 2009). As matter that we must negotiate, products shape our daily experience in ways that

spark particular stories and thoughts, and designers can therefore influence what these thoughts are. As Julia Lohman describes: when communicating through objects the meaning is created through the materiality of the object. The materials become words; the design becomes the syntax. The piece speaks without the detour of language (Williams, 2012).

The level at which *materialism* manifests – arguably the site of human-made ecological destruction – occurs within the dynamic shallows. The *epipelagic zone* (the shallow part of the ocean, in which the majority of marine life can be found) is populated by a dynamic and shifting mass of manufactured products. This constantly shifting assemblage is deployed to reflect our equally dynamic and unstable identities. As our identities evolve and change, so too must the products we deploy to both mirror and project these ephemeral ideas. This form of materialistic value orientation (MVO) involves the belief that it is important to continually pursue the culturally sanctioned goals of attaining, financial success, having nice possessions, having the right image, and having a high status (Kasser, 2004). In this way, *materialism* is defined as 'the importance a consumer attaches to worldly possessions' (Belk, 1984, p291) or 'a set of centrally held beliefs about the importance of possessions in one's life' (Richins & Dawson, 1992, p308), particularly in terms of their ability to communicate one's societal position, to others. The products of MVO tend to inhabit the shallows of our material worlds, as opposed to the very different mode of engagement occurring at the depths. In this way, it is clear that material possessions gain social meaning not only because they have instrumental use in sustaining and developing our daily lives but also because they function as symbols of identity, personality and self-expression (Dittmar & Pepper, 1994).

Down at the very depths of material experience, enduring associations between people and things are not wholly designable. After all, 'for personal reasons one can feel emotionally attached even to a turnip or a hubcap' (van Hinte, 1997, p234). This is because each user possesses a unique assemblage of memories and experiences, which render objects as vigorous symbols of the self, and carriers of great personal significance. Over 40-years earlier, Benedict in, *Patterns of Culture* (1955), asserted that '[n]o man ever looks at the world with pristine eyes. He sees it edited by a definite set of customs and institutions and ways of thinking (Benedict, 1955, p2).

Hadal or epipelagic – toward depth appropriate design

We can design for greater depths of emotional experience in several ways. We can specify materials that age gracefully, and that develop a quality and patina over time; functionality can also be approached in this way, whereby a product's performance and capability evolves and improves over time. We can design products that are easier to repair, upgrade and maintain. The challenge here is reframe the act of repair as a partisan act – a rich and integral aspect of the user experience. In the emotionally durable design

context, repair is forward-facing process of improvement, not one simply of reverting back to a former state. These are just a few emotionally durable design strategies, and while some of these come at an increased cost to manufacturers, they generate revenue downstream, through the introduction of service and upgrade.

It sounds peculiar to be proposing a commercial environment in which we encourage people to keep products for longer, and therefore sell less products! This, in many ways, runs contrary to the dominant model of capitalism; a fairly superficial idea, in which the more you sell equates to the level of success you have attained. However, we can look at this a different way. Take a pair of Puma sneakers, for example. One thing we know about these sneakers is that one-day, at some point in their life, they will wear out and the user (or, *consumer*, as economists like to call them) will need to replace them; that much, we know. However, what we don't know is which brand the user will choose? Will they replace them with a nice new pair from Puma, or will they be less loyal, and try a pair of Nikes this time? So often we hear opposition against longer-lasting products being based on such a story, where brand managers feel concerned that encouraging people to keep things for longer will affect the bottom-line. However there is a deep assumption lurking here, which is that repeat purchases will be with you, and that your customers are, indeed, brand loyal. I argue that by allowing customers to keep their products for longer, you nurture a deeper relationship with both the product and the brand, and in so doing, increase the likelihood of brand loyalty maturing. In this way, emotionally durable design can be seen as a commercially viable strategy for sustaining and growing market share, through building customer loyalty.

Until recently sustainable design methodologies have seldom engaged with the more fundamental questions such as the meaning and place of products in our lives, and the contribution of materials goods to what might be broadly termed, the human endeavour (Walker, 2006). Indeed, simply having more stuff stopped making people in Britain happier decades ago. The New Economics Foundation (NEF) argue for an economy of better, not more. One of things that last and can be repaired many times before being recycled, allowing us to share better the surplus of stuff we already have (NEF, 2012). We are currently experiencing a seismic shift in thinking, from the design and delivery of short-life products, to that of longer-lasting material experiences and services. It follows, then, that during product development, designers and manufacturers have a moral obligation to consider longevity and minimized lifecycle impacts (Van Nes & Cramer, 2005; Cooper, 2005). Consumers need to be aware of life spans and lifecycle impacts when buying products (Cooper & Christer, 2005).

Designing longer-lasting products without a clear understanding of the depth at which you are engaging users, is like packing a suitcase for a trip to an unknown destination, and not knowing what you will be doing when you get there. The picture is incomplete,

and forces gross generalisations to be made. As stated earlier, there are clear discrepancies between the products that matter, and the products we deploy as signifiers of identity and social position, for example. In conflating these two aspects of material experience, results risk distortion, and insight becomes misleading, and the impact of product life research is limited.

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